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THE IMPACT OF ISLAMIC SOCIAL FINANCE INSTRUMENTS ON THE SOCIAL SPHERE: THE CASE OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS USING ISLAMIC SOCIAL FINANCE INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract

The paper explores the burgeoning influence of Islamic social finance, focusing on the huge impact and contribution of traditional Islamic social finance instruments. Due to their nature and scope in terms of social good, ethical principles have driven Islamic social finance to the forefront in the wake of recent economic and political uncertainties.

It puts into perspective the trends and activities of three major Waqf and zakat institutions, after which an elaboration of their various contributions to the social sphere is further done. The article covers financial aspects dealing with income sources generated by these institutions and enumerates their statistical contributions in recent years.

Analyzing these important facets of Waqf and zakat, the article goes deep into the practical implementation and impacts that the principles of Islamic social finance have. It concludes by summarizing the findings and providing some general conclusions with regard to the potential of Waqf and zakat in addressing social challenges.

Keywords: Islamic Social Finance, Waqf, Zakat, Sadaqah, Endowment Funds, Social Impact, Islamic Economics, Social Welfare, Sustainable Development, Poverty Alleviation.

Introduction.

Against the background of a world characterized by increasing socio-economic disparities and rising awareness of ethical finance, the instruments of Islamic social finance are steadily gaining notoriety not just within Muslim-majority countries but worldwide [7]. Grounded in the cornerstones of social justice, redistribution of wealth, and development of society, these emerging tools carry a fresh approach to dealing with societal challenges. Of the myriad tools of Islamic social finance (ISF), waqf and zakat holds a special place on account of its tremendous potential to make long-term impacts in sustainability in areas of social concern.

Waqf would translate in a general sense to an Islamic endowment, meaning the allowance of assets to accrue for perpetual social benefit. Waqf draws inspiration from centuries of tradition and practice in philanthropy guided by Islamic legal principles and has played a very pivotal role through history in promoting education, healthcare, poverty alleviation, and infrastructure development within various circles of the Muslim community [18]. The ideas of Islamic finance have today found more resonance with an increased audience looking for ethical and impactful investment avenues, and Waqf therefore is also undergoing a revival of sorts, now being adapted to suit the needs of today.

Economists often examine the issue of economic inequality by repeatedly going back to the idea of Zakat. Zakat is an effective method to promote a fairer sharing of wealth [14]. Zakat enables increased investment opportunities, higher consumption levels, and funding for community initiatives. Zakat is a compulsory donation for Muslims as part of their religious beliefs. Muslims who possess a certain minimum amount of wealth must donate 2,5% of their liquid assets to charity annually [17].

This paper presents the current influence of Islamic social finance instruments on fostering positive social change, focusing on the case of waqf and zakat. It describes how waqf and zakat can help solve some pressing social problems by looking at the mechanisms of operation, and contemporary uses. We also detail the activities and contributions of major waqf and zakat institutions in this paper and give an overview of their financial models and what tangible outputs have been produced from their work. On this journey, we hope to add to the understanding of waqf and zakat as a powerful tool for sustainable development and social good.

Literature review. Islamic social finance can be described as a branch of Islamic finance offering non-profit products and services [15]. Islamic social finance is also called "Islamic social safety nets", which is also a charitable sector.

The goals of Islamic social finance are to reduce unemployment and poverty [1], to help improve the socio-economic status of disadvantaged groups, to implement social justice in distribution, and to grow the economy [5]. In other words, it is aimed at strengthening the social economy in the society [13]. Islamic social finance also includes non-profit finance aimed at social benefits and socially oriented finance for profit, which means it has a wider scope than social finance.

Islamic social finance helps poor and financially distressed families to restore their place in society and prevent them from becoming more financially vulnerable [12]. The amount of zakat that Muslims have to pay every year is so large that if it was properly disposed of, there would not be a poor Muslim left in the world.

Scholars have different opinions on what instruments should be included in Islamic social finance. According to Arumsari and Rikavati [4], zakat, infak, sadaqah and waqf are major instruments of Islamic social finance. Similarly, Ascarya [5], Shuaib and Sohail [24]

also mention these four instruments as the instruments of ISF. Abdullahi and et al. [2] include zakat, sadaqah and waqf as instruments of ISF. Umar and et al. [26] add Islamic microfinance to the list consisting of zakat and waqf as ISF instruments.

From the above, it can be concluded that major ISF instruments are zakat, waqf and sadaqah.

The word “zakat” means “purity” and “growth” in Arabic [23]. Zakat is one of the five pillars of Islam and is an obligatory payment for Muslims that aims to purify the heart and wealth of a person, and leads to socio-economic justice through sharing and caring [22]. Although zakat is often seen as an Islamic prayer, it is actually a component of the social and financial system of Islam [3].

Zakat can play an important role in ensuring socio-economic security in modern society, its sources come from property in the form of commercial enterprises, savings, shares, gold and silver, wealth, property, and agricultural products [9]. Zakat is paid at the usual rate of 2,5 percent for wealth and income, but from 2,5 to 20 percent for agricultural products, precious metals, minerals and livestock, depending on their type.

Infak etymologically means “to spend treasure” in Arabic [19]. In Islamic jurisprudence, infak is the giving or spending of property for worship or other permissible activities. Infak influences the distribution of income [8].

Sadaqah is etymologically derived from Arabic (sincerity) and means “charity” [19]. Sadaqah can also be an intangible quality that is not related to quantity, time, and is not limited to material. In Islamic Sharia, charity means praying by spending part of one’s property, which is not obligatory.

The waqf has been used by Muslims for over one thousand four hundred years for education, poverty eradication, education, preservation of architectural and artistic heritage, conservation of public lands, and can still be successfully used to create funds to eradicate all forms of poverty [25]. Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf in his work “Kifoya” describes waqf as follows [23]: in Sharia, waqf means spending the profit to make a sacrifice to Allah while maintaining the original of a good. By endowing, the profits from something are continued for its users. According to Sadeq, one of the important strategies to reduce poverty is charity, which has the potential to overcome it [21]. There are many forms of charity, but the long-lasting one is the institution of waqf in the Islamic

ethical system, which has the characteristic of “eternity”.

Effective investment of waqf funds can be a catalyst for economic development, creating opportunities for communities and stimulating entrepreneurship. By channeling funds into vital projects such as small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) or infrastructure development, waqf institutions can stimulate economic growth [20], create employment and reduce poverty [10]. This approach not only maximizes financial returns, but also empowers people and communities to become self-sufficient.

Research methodology. In this work, the term Islamic social finance and its components are defined in a systematic analysis. After that, the activity of international organizations using ISF instruments are analyzed through their statistics. In this process methods such as systematic analysis of socio-economic phenomena, scientific abstraction, empirical, grouping, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparative and dynamic analysis, systematic approach, monographic observation, statistical and economic analysis are used in the work.

Discussion and results. International organizations using Islamic social finance instruments are expanding day by day. They are also successfully operating in Muslim and non-Muslim countries. The first organization we will explore is Awqaf Properties Investment Fund (APIF), one of the organizations successfully operating in the above-mentioned field. Recognizing the significant development potential of waqf, the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) pioneered the financing of a number of waqf projects prior to the establishment of APIF. These projects are among the first efforts of the Islamic Development Bank to financially support the waqf concept. Later, in 1997, APIF was founded based on the approval of the 6th meeting of the ministers of the member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation in Jakarta, Indonesia [31].

APIF was established in 2001 by IDB in cooperation with nine other institutes with a total subscription of 50 million US dollars. As of December 31, 2022, APIF has 19 participants (members) with a total capital of 114,51 million US dollars. Among them are IDB, Waqf ministries, Waqf organizations, non-profit organizations, Islamic banks and individual investors. As of 2022, its total assets amounted to almost 142 million US dollars. Over the past 15 years, this indicator has doubled (Figure 1).

Figure 1. APIF's total assets over the years (2008-2022) [30]

Today, IDB has extended a 100 million US dollars line of financing to use in financing APIF projects.

In order to continue to support the development of the waqf sectors through APIF, IDB has approved three technical assistance grants of 200000 US dollars,

275000 US dollars and 280000 US dollars for feasibility studies, property appraisals and legal services [6].

In 2022, the countries with the highest APIF financing projects were Saudi Arabia (\$73 million) and the United States (\$62 million), followed by countries such as Iran, Uganda, Sudan and the UAE [6].

Figure 2. Distribution of approved APIF projects by country in 2022 [6]

On average, APIF projects generate USD 1 million (2022 y.) in sustainable annual income for beneficiary organizations after disbursement of IDB funding [6].

Figure 3. APIF capital investments 2018-2022 (million US dollars) [6]

Looking at the figure 3, we can see the latest APIF capital investments for 2018-2022. In 2019, there were not capital investments, however in 2020, a significant increase was seen in capital investment, reaching almost 20 million US dollars. It can be noticed that this

indicator decreased relatively in the following years, which can be assessed as the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent recovery period.

Figure 4. Structure of APIF investments in 2021-2022 (million US dollars) [6]

Figure 4 shows the dynamics of APIF's investments in Islamic financial instruments in recent years.

In 2021, lease and sukuk instruments accounted for the

largest share of them. In 2022, the total value of investments in 2021 remained almost unchanged at 70 million US dollars, only certain structural changes were observed [6].

APIF was established to develop waqf properties on a global scale. APIF has played an important role in developing the waqf sector worldwide through technical assistance and project financing. This fund presented a concept that proves the viability of such an impact-investment model for the endowment. Moreover, it has created momentum in the sector and encouraged the creation of a supportive environment for waqf, even initiating macro-level reforms such as the adoption of waqf laws in several IDB member countries. APIF helped institutionalize ITB's approach to promoting waqf by funding the development of waqf real estate properties.

The second organization, Islamic Relief Worldwide (IRW), which operates using Islamic social finance instruments, is headquartered in the United Kingdom. The Islamic Relief Worldwide organization was founded in 1984 by Dr. Hani El-Banna and fellow students at the University of Birmingham in Great Britain in response to a famine in Africa. They went door-to-door, and collected money for the food of the people suffering from famine [27]. In 1985, IRW started its first project – sponsoring a chicken farm in Sudan. In the same year, its founders opened a small office in

Moseley, Birmingham, where they raised 100,000 pounds for the fight against hunger.

Funds come to various offices of IRW through the instruments of Islamic social finance, such as waqf, zakat, and sadaqah. In 2022, IRW's global revenue reached 234 million pounds [11]. The donors with the largest share of this income are IRW offices located in the USA, Great Britain and Canada (Figure 5). Notably, the income from endowment investment to IRW in 2022 was 600,000 pounds, which in turn indicates that the organization has effectively been operating endowment investment.

In 2022, the total expenditure of the IRW organization was 193,3 million pounds. In figure 6, we can see the cost structure of the IRW organization. The biggest part of the expenditure was almost 110 million pounds for humanitarian aid. Since the organization is socially oriented, the main funds are humanitarian aid; caring for orphans and children; health care, water, sanitation and hygiene; we can see that it is spent on such purposes as supporting education.

IRW's Sustainable Livelihoods Program is a program aimed at creating financial inclusion in low-income countries, enabling poor people to become financially self-sufficient. In 2022, IRW's microfinance programs reached 43,500 people living in poverty, with 10 million pounds invested in the program [11].

Figure 5. Sources of IRW revenue in 2022 (million pounds) [11]

In 2022, IRW reached over 17,3 million people in over 35 countries worldwide [11] (Table 1).

Figure 6. Cost structure of the IRW organization in 2022 (million pounds) [11]

As can be seen from table 1, the countries covered by IRW's extensive assistance have been mainly in the African and Asian regions. Yemen (3,5 million), Nigeria (2 million) and Afghanistan (1,2 million) have been the countries most affected by IRW [11].

Looking at the sources of income of Islamic Relief Worldwide, we can divide the sources of IRW income into three directions:

- Funds from IRW offices in different countries;
- Grants and funds received from institutions and

other important donors around the world to finance specific projects;

– Income from trading subsidiaries ("TIC International", the main activity of which is earning income through clothing processing), the International Endowment Fund and other investments.

The third source of IRW's income given above is of great importance to our research, therefore we will look into them.

Table 1.

Distribution of people assisted by IRW in 2022 by country [11]

№	Name of Countries	Number of people	№	Name of Countries	Number of people
1	Yemen	3560269	20	Turkey	96735
2	Nigeria	2013734	21	Philippines	87714
3	Afghanistan	1239724	22	Lebanon	86474
4	Pakistan	1214985	23	Nepal	84377
5	Somalia	1134739	24	Indonesia	79476
6	Sudan	1088452	25	Tunisia	78450
7	Syria	999392	26	Iraq	66251
8	Occupied Palestinian Territory (Gaza)	993710	27	Myanmar	66119
9	Bangladesh	892202	28	South Africa	50742
10	Mali	878934	29	Albania	48092
11	Ethiopia	723424	30	India	39109
12	Kenya	460106	31	Bosnia and Herzegovina	32386
13	Malawi	333822	32	Russian Federation (Chechnya)	22002
14	South Sudan	298769	33	Madagascar	9262
15	Kosovo	141733	34	Spain	5036
16	Jordan	135267	35	Italy	1946
17	North Macedonia	124179	36	Moldova	838
18	United Kingdom	123194	37	Malaysia	810
19	Sri Lanka	108387		Total	17,3 million

TIC International Ltd (TIC) is a clothing recycling business and a subsidiary that operates a chain of charity shops. Its main role is to generate income for IRW to run its programs, while providing a valuable environmental service by recycling clothing that would otherwise end up in landfills and harm the environment. In addition to its business activities, TIC has played an important role in providing employment to local people in the UK Midlands over the past decades. In 2022, 1931 tonnes of unwanted clothes were turned into 242000 pounds by reselling and recycling them into quality clothes in IRW stores.

IRW maintains endowments invested in real estate in Great Britain. Funds from these investments are spent on humanitarian and social development programs designated by donors. IRW Endowment fund grew to 8,4 million pounds in 2022 thanks to endowment donations and investment returns [11].

The Board of Trustees of IRW monitors the proper investment of funds and the proper management of the risks associated with them.

Another organization working on zakat, one of the main instruments of Islamic social finance, is the National Zakat Foundation (NZF), which was established in 2011 and which accepts zakat and other Islamic donations and grants to those in need across the UK [28].

It is worth mentioning that after the success of the National Zakat Fund in Great Britain, which was launched in 2011, the NZF platform was also implemented in Australia and Canada. In 2016, the National

Zakat Foundation Worldwide was established as a central body connecting the activities of various local platforms. Today, Australia, Canada, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Great Britain and Germany are considered members of the National Zakat Fund Worldwide [29].

It is appropriate to review the activities of the National Zakat Fund in Great Britain, as the country that started the activities of the NZF first among the countries mentioned above.

Since the launch of the NZF in the UK, more than 59000 people have been helped, with a total of 31,7 million pounds in zakat distributed by the fund [16].

According to the NZF, in 2022, 17131 needy people in the UK were helped through zakat, and 5,57 million pounds of zakat was distributed to the needy.

NZF provides assistance in the following 3 categories [28]:

1. Hardship relief fund: helps Muslims get out of difficult situations by providing emergency funds to cover necessities such as food and clothing;
2. Housing and work fund: helps Muslims to get a job, find affordable housing and work skills to support themselves and their families;
3. Education fund: Helps strengthen society by investing in the education and development of Muslim scholars and other community leaders eligible for zakat.

Among the above funds, the most supported type in 2022 was the “Hardship relief fund” (Table 2).

Table 2.

Distribution of grants from NZF funds in 2022 [16]

Type of funds	People helped by the Foundation		Zakat distributed by fund	
	number of people	%	million pounds	%
Hardship relief fund	14675	86	3,8	68
Housing and work fund	2350	14	1,2	20
Educational fund	106	less than 1	0,5	12
Total	17131	100	5,5	100

NZF’s total revenue for 2022 was 7,8 million pounds (2021: 6,3 million pounds) [16]. Among the

revenue streams, the largest amount of money was received by the “Hardship relief fund” (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Sources of NZF income for 2021-2022 (million pounds) [16]

The return on investment in 2022 was 10253 pounds. This figure was 2288 pounds in 2021 which was almost four times less than in 2022 [16]. It can be

concluded that NZF has been conducting investment activities effectively.

Figure 7. NZF investment income (pounds) for 2021-2022 [16]

The National Zakat Fund makes short-term investments through interest-free cash deposits and property investments through a third-party investment management company. The objective of NZF's investment policy is to obtain Shariah-compliant returns from safe deposits and other similar investments, while minimizing risks as much as possible.

In 2022, the NZF Board introduced a separate Risk Management Committee to oversee risk management. To reduce risk, cash for short-term deposits is kept only in banks with high credit ratings, and real estate investments are low-risk, short-term, and credit risk is assessed.

Above, we considered the international organizations that use the instruments of Islamic social finance. Their main activity is the purposeful distribution of funds received from donors as waqf, zakat, sadaqah and other traditional charitable instruments, which are considered instruments of Islamic social finance. But it has recently been observed that their sources of income do not depend only on the funds coming from these donors, but they are also engaged in investment activities through existing funds. This do not only bring in more funds for the implementation of their socially oriented goals and activities, but also help prevent the organizations from becoming dependent on donors in the long term.

Conclusion.

We can see through the experiences of leading international organizations that Islamic social financing tools are effective mechanisms for meeting social needs and promoting inclusive development in Islamic and non-Islamic societies. Through the principles of zakat, sadaqah, waqf and other instruments, Islamic societies have been able to reduce poverty, promote education and health care, and other areas for sustainable development. The holistic approach of these instruments not only improves the well-being of individuals or families, but also strengthens the sense of solidarity in society.

In addition, the evaluation of the impact of these instruments has shown their ability to create positive effects beyond direct aid. Using the concepts of sustainable funding and responsible governance, Islamic social finance instruments provide the basis for long-term social and economic empowerment.

Furthermore, the deep impact of Islamic social finance instruments on the social sphere cannot be denied. Their ability to meet the needs of social welfare and development while respecting the principles of

equality and solidarity makes them an invaluable instrument for building an inclusive and sustainable society. As Islamic finance develops, it is necessary to recognize the key role of these instruments in creating a just and compassionate society.

References

1. Abduh M. The role of Islamic social finance in achieving SDG number 2: end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture //Al-Shajarah: Journal of the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization (ISTAC). – 2019.
2. Abdullahi A., Othman A. H. A., Kassim S. Financial inclusion enhancement through the adoption of Islamic microfinance in Nigeria //International Journal of Ethics and Systems. – 2021. – T. 37. – №. 3. – C. 486-505.
3. Al Qardawi, Yusuf, & Monzer, Kahf. Fikh Al Zakah. Saudi Arabia: Scientific Publishing Centre King Abdulaziz University Jeddah. – 2000.
4. Arumsari V., Rikawati R. Islamic social funds: enabling the unable to be able //Journal of Applied Business Administration. – 2020. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 88-97.
5. Ascarya A. The role of Islamic social finance during Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia's economic recovery //International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management. – 2022. – T. 15. – №. 2. – C. 386-405.
6. Awqaf Properties Investment Fund. Annual Report, 2022 // <https://www.isdb.org/apif/publications>.
7. Ayub, M. (2018). Institutionalising 'waqf' for realising the shared development objective by Islamic banks and financial institutions. *Editorial, Journal of Islamic Business and Management (JIBM)*, 8(2).
8. Aziz F., Mahmud M., Karim E. The Nature of Infaq and its Effects on Distribution of Wealth. – 2008.
9. Cattelan V. (ed.). Islamic social finance: Entrepreneurship, cooperation and the sharing economy. – Routledge, 2018. – p. 198.
10. Elasrag H. Towards a new role of the institution of waqf //Available at SSRN 3011290. – 2017.
11. Islamic Relief Worldwide. Annual report and financial statements 2022. // <https://islamic-relief.org/about-us/annual-reports/>
12. Islom moliyasi, Zakot, Sadaqa, Vaqf va Qarzi Hasan, 2022. // <https://islommoliyasi.uz/uz/zakot-sadaqa-waqf-va-qarz-hasana/> (Accessed: 12.09.2024).

13. Kuanova L. A., Sagiyeva R., Shirazi N. S. Islamic social finance: a literature review and future research directions //Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research. – 2021. – T. 12. – №. 5. – C. 707-728.
14. Kuzudisli A. Fight against poverty from the Islamic point of view: the wealth distribution and share //Economics World. – 2017. – T. 5. – №. 1. – C. 9-15.
15. Mustafa Z. et al. Islamic social finance and its roles in developing Islamic economy in addressing various issues during the COVID-19 pandemic //AZ (AZKA-PPZ) (Ed.), Islamic social finance: The way forward. – 2022. – C. 133.
16. National Zakat Foundation. Impact report and financial statements 2022.
17. Obaidullah M., Manap T. A. A. Behavioral dimensions of Islamic philanthropy: The case of zakat //Financial Inclusion and Poverty Alleviation: Perspectives from Islamic Institutions and Instruments. – 2017. – C. 219-243.
18. Omar, H. H., & Sanyinna, A. Y. (2018). Administrative challenges of WAQF institution in the contemporary world: Future prospects. *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 294-299.
19. Ritonga M. A., Mahyudin E. Review of Zakat, Infaq, and Shadaqah as a Similar Terminology //Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Recent Innovations (ICRI 2018). – 2020. – C. 801-808.
20. Saad A. Y. Q. et al. The prospect of Waqf in financing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Yemen. – 2022.
21. Sadeq A. H. M. Waqf, perpetual charity and poverty alleviation //International Journal of Social Economics. – 2002. – T. 29. – №. 1/2. – C. 135-151.
22. Saud, M.A. Contemporary Zakat. Ohio: Zakat and Research Foundation. – 1988.
23. Shayx Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. Kifoya. 2-juz. – T.: “Hilol-Nashr”, 2022.
24. Shuaib A. A., Sohail M. The role of Islamic social finance in societal welfare: a case study of selected IFBOs in southwest Nigeria //International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management. – 2022. – T. 15. – №. 1. – C. 83-99.
25. Syed H., Genç S. Y. Poverty in Muslim Countries: Policy Recommendations Over the Gukf Cooperation Council //International Congress of Islamic Economy, Finance and Ethics, December, 2019.
26. Umar U. H. et al. The potential of Islamic social finance to alleviate poverty in the era of COVID-19: the moderating effect of ethical orientation //International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management. – 2022. – T. 15. – №. 2. – C. 255-270.
27. <https://islamic-relief.org/> (Accessed: 13.09.2024).
28. <https://nzf.org.uk/> (Accessed 13.09.2024).
29. <https://nzfworldwide.com/membership/> (Accessed 13.09.2024).
30. <https://www.isdb.org/apif/> (Accessed: 13.09.2024).
31. <https://www.isdb.org/apif/about-apif> (Accessed: 13.09.2024).